

Integration between real estate and stock markets: Evidence from the Philippines¹

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Abstract

Real estate and stocks are two significant asset class in an investor's portfolio. In order to shed light on how to optimize a portfolio and achieve asset diversification, the purpose of this study is to explore the link between these two markets. The study results show that the two markets are regarded as highly integrated using cointegration and vector error correction modeling methodologies, as well as data from the stock and real estate markets from 2000Q2 to 2022Q1. They suggest that while real estate and stock markets are good alternatives for investment allocation, investors cannot gain the benefits of diversity by building a portfolio that includes both the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines. Furthermore, the positive effects of stock prices on real estate corroborate the wealth effect hypothesis, which states that stock market contribute positively to the rise in real estate market. This suggests that house prices are rather high, and real estate is used considerably more as an investment vehicle.

Keywords: Real estate market, Stock market, Integration, VECH, Portfolio management

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Introduction:

Real estate and stocks are two significant asset classes in an investor's portfolio. Both have the potential to provide investors with high returns and diversification benefits. According to Oikarinen (2010), real estate is a somewhat less liquid and pricey investment whereas equities are a very liquid and practical investment for investors. However, little is known about the relationship between these two markets in the Philippines, and whether they can be effectively used to achieve diversification.

The Philippine economy has been experiencing significant growth in recent years, driven by various factors such as increasing foreign investments, rising consumer demand, and a favorable business climate. As a result, investors are becoming more interested in the Philippine market, and are looking for ways to optimize their investment portfolios.

Real estate and stocks are two major asset classes that investors consider when building their portfolios. Both asset classes offer the potential for high returns and can serve as diversification tools. However, there is limited research on the relationship between the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines, and whether they can effectively be used for portfolio diversification. The stock market plays a significant role in the financial sector's efforts to support economic growth. The stock market may direct investments into the most productive technology, resulting in economic growth, by lowering the cost of mobilizing savings (Greenwood and Smith 1997). Additionally, the stock market offers market liquidity that permits the implementation of lengthy projects with lengthy payoffs, supporting a nation's economic progress (Bencivenga et al. 1996; Levine 1991). Arestis et al. (2001) assert that the growth of the stock market reduces the risk associated with financial assets and facilitates simple access to cash for businesses through equity issuances. This improves capital allocation and creates a pathway for economic expansion. The Philippine stock market has grown dramatically in recent decades. PSEi, the share price index, climbed from 1,869 points in 1997 to 7,230 points in 2014 (PSE, 2000-2014; World Federation of Exchanges [WFE], 2015). The successive increase of the PSEi from 2009 to 2014 demonstrated the growth momentum, with a cumulative growth

of 286 percent in these six years (WFE, 2015). Furthermore, the size of the stock market as assessed by the market capitalisation ratio can show the country's amazing growth. The PSE rose from 55th in 2005 to 12th in 2014. (World Development Indicators [WDI], 2016). Meanwhile, the high demand for houses and offices, backed by government-sponsored infrastructure development plans, has kept the real estate sector growing well over the past few years. It made up about 11% of the nation's GDP in 2019. The consistent rise in the real estate sector's gross value added since 2009 is another indicator of its expansion. PSA (2019 B) reports that the sector's gross value added was PHP281.595 billion, up 7% from 2018.

Existing literature (Darrat and Glascock, 1989; Liu et al., 1990; Li and Wang, 1995; Poterba et al., 1995; Ling and Naranjo, 1999; Green, 2002; Kapopoulos and Siokis, 2005) is inconclusive on the relationship between stock and real estate property - a contentious issue for researchers and policymakers. One school of thought holds that real estate property values and stock prices are positively related (Kim, 1993; Chen and Lee, 1998), while another holds that they are negatively related. The debate of the relationship between the stock and real estate markets widened to include the concept of wealth and the credit-price effect of the two markets.

This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the link between the Philippine real estate and stock markets, and examining their implications for portfolio diversification. By analyzing data from the stock and real estate markets from 2000Q2 to 2022Q1, this study will use cointegration and error correction modeling methodologies to investigate the relationship between these two markets. The results of this study will contribute to the literature on portfolio diversification by providing insights into the potential benefits of investing in real estate and stocks in the Philippines. The findings may help investors make informed decisions on how to optimize their portfolios and achieve diversification. Additionally, the results of this study may also be of interest to policymakers and market participants who are looking to better understand the dynamics of the Philippine real estate and stock markets.

Statement of the Problem

The primary objective of this study is to examine the relationship between real estate and stock markets in the Philippines using data from 2000Q2 to 2022Q1. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Determine the degree of integration between the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines using cointegration and error correction modeling methodologies.
2. Examine the nature of the Granger causality between real estate prices and stock prices.
3. Provide recommendations to investors on how to optimize their portfolio by considering the relationship between real estate and stock markets in the Philippines.

Statement of Assumptions

Null hypothesis (H_0): Real estate market is not statistically significant in explaining stock prices.

Alternative hypothesis (H_a): Real estate market is statistically significant in explaining stock prices.

Operational Definition of Terms

Determinants are factors that influence housing prices, such as, stock price index, real interest rate.

Housing Price Index (HPI) measures the rate of change at which the prices of residential properties (e.g., flats, detached houses, terraced houses, etc.) purchased by households change over time. It includes new and existing dwellings, independent of their final use and previous owner. The index included land and residential buildings but excluded purchases through in-house financing and direct construction of the property owners. In this study, the housing price index is being used as a proxy for real estate market.

Stock market index (SMI) is an index that measures a stock market. The data for the stock market is represented by the annual transactions at the Philippine Stock Exchange.

Interest rate (IR) is the cost of borrowing money measured in percentage.

I. Literature Review

The relationship between real estate and stock markets has been the subject of numerous studies in the USA (Liow and Yang, 2005; Li et al., 2015; Hui and Chan, 2018; Zheng and Osmer, 2019); UK (Hui et al., 2011; Hui and Chan, 2013; Bouri et al., 2019); Germany (Gokmenoglu and Hesami, 2019); Greece (Gounopoulos et al., 2019); and Taiwan (Wang et al., 2017). To the best of our knowledge, no one has examined into the relationship between real estate and stocks in the Philippines. Hence, the purpose of this study is to study the link between the Philippine real estate and stock markets and examine the implications for portfolio diversification.

Investigating asset integration is essential because, if markets are integrated, the benefits of portfolio diversification will be diminished. A plethora of studies have looked into the global convergence of the real estate and stock industries. Using data from 1971 to 1973, Wilson and Okunev (1999) examined the integration between the real estate and stock markets of the USA, UK, and Australia. With the help of the fractional cointegration methodology, it discovers that while there is no correlation between real estate and the stock market in the USA and UK, there is a strong correlation in Australia. In the United States and the United Kingdom from 1974 to 2009, McMillan (2012) discovered a sizable cointegration between stock prices and real estate values. The cointegration between the Greek real estate and stock markets from 1997 to 2015 was documented by Gounopoulos et al. in 2019. In order to explore the short- and long-term causal linkages between series, Yousaf, I., and Ali, S. (2020) applied the Johansen cointegration test and the vector error correction model to the integration of the real estate and stock markets in Pakistan. They discovered a cointegration between the stock market and the real estate markets. They imply that real estate and stock markets are suitable alternatives for investment allocation, but that diversification benefits cannot be obtained by Pakistani investors while building a portfolio of real estate and stocks.

In contrast, Wang et al. (2017) found no evidence of cointegration between Taiwan's real estate and stock markets. It means that portfolio investors can spread their risks by

building a portfolio of Taiwanese stocks and real estate. According to the aforementioned literature, none of the recent research have looked into Pakistan's real estate and stock market's integration. Only Umar et al. (2019) looked at how Pakistan's monetary policies affected the country's housing sector. It was discovered that tight monetary policy causes a drop in housing values and vice versa.

The literature suggests that both real estate and stocks are viable alternative investments that can provide diversification benefits to a portfolio. Real estate has historically been considered a safe haven asset, providing stable returns and acting as a hedge against inflation. On the other hand, stocks are known for their high returns and liquidity, making them an attractive investment for many investors.

Real estate and stocks are two major asset classes that have been studied extensively in the literature on alternative investments and portfolio diversification. Real estate has traditionally been considered a good alternative investment because of its low correlation with other asset classes, such as stocks and bonds (Geltner & Miller, 2001). Real estate has also been shown to have high risk-adjusted returns (Gibson & Moulaert, 2014) and can serve as a hedge against inflation (Ibbotson & Kaplan, 2000).

Similarly, stocks have been a popular investment option for investors seeking high returns and diversification benefits. Stocks offer the potential for high returns due to the growth potential of the underlying companies, and they can also provide diversification benefits when combined with other asset classes (Elton et al., 2007).

Recent studies have also examined the potential benefits of combining real estate and stocks in a diversified portfolio. For example, Liu and Ward (2010) found that adding real estate investment trusts (REITs) to a mixed-asset portfolio could enhance diversification and reduce portfolio volatility. Other studies have also found evidence of a positive relationship between real estate and stock market returns, suggesting that the two markets are highly integrated (Jaffe & Cai, 1996; Chen et al., 2002).

Despite the growing interest in real estate and stocks as alternative investments, there is limited research on the link between these two markets in the Philippines. This is an important gap in the literature because the Philippines is a rapidly developing market with significant growth potential, and understanding the relationship between real estate and stocks could have important implications for investors looking to optimize their portfolios in this market.

In light of these research gaps, this study aims to explore the link between the Philippine real estate and stock markets, and examine their implications for portfolio diversification. By analyzing data from 2000Q2 to 2022Q1, this study will use cointegration and error correction modeling methodologies to investigate the relationship between these two markets. The findings of this study may help investors make informed decisions on how to optimize their portfolios and achieve diversification, and may also be of interest to policymakers and market participants looking to better understand the dynamics of the Philippine real estate and stock markets.

Methodology

This study will use cointegration and error correction modeling methodologies to analyze the relationship between the Philippine real estate and stock markets. The study will use data from the stock and real estate markets from 2000Q2 to 2020Q1.

This chapter discusses the research design framework and methodologies, as well as data collecting, analysis, and treatment. The formulation and operationalization of such concepts into quantifiable things is critical for guiding empirical study. The study design employs a quantitative statistical analysis strategy that makes use of secondary data.

Research Environment

The research is limited to the Philippines. As illustrated in Figure 3, the research area is located in a developing country (dark gray), where the standard of life, income, economic, and industrial development remains below average.

Figure 2

Location Map

Source: WorldData.info (2021)

Data Collection:

The data used in this study was collected from the Yahoo Finance and Philippine Stock Exchange (PSE) and the Bank for International Settlements (BIS). The PSE index is used in this study as a proxy for the Philippine stock market. The PSE index data is obtained from the Yahoo Finance website. Data for real estate indices is sourced from the renowned Bank International Settlements (BIS) website. Quarterly data is used from 2000Q2 to 2022Q1 to determine the link between real estate and the stock market. After corrections, the total number of observations based on quarterly data is 88. Finally, a control variable, such as the interest rate, is employed for robustness testing. The World

Bank website is where the quarterly interest rate statistics are obtained. All data were transformed to natural logs.

Research Procedures

The section of the paper that follows provides an outline of statistical theory that is required to answer the research question and achieve the goal of this study. The relationship between stock prices and property prices was investigated using time series econometric approaches. The study established a linear link between housing prices (HP), stock prices (SP), and interest rates (IR). Then, started with property pricing for the entire country.

The following equations illustrates the estimations in this study

$$HP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 SP_{it} + \beta_2 IR_{it} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

$$SP_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 HP_{it} + \beta_2 IR_{it} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

Where i indicates house prices for the respectively parts.

As previously stated, the presence of nonstationary variables and spurious relationships must be considered while evaluating the relationship between variables in this scenario. As a result, a regression between variables may produce a significant result even if there is no underlying relationship. As a result, the result has no real economic value. (Granger and Newbold 1974) Engel and Granger (1987) provide a solution that

eliminates this difficulty while still allowing inference of the link between non-stationary time series without data loss. Certain assumptions must be met in order to accomplish this. This is elaborated on more below (Engle and Granger, 1987).

Before modeling the series together, this study applied unit root tests to each series to test for stationarity. According to Granger and Newbold (1974), this should be done to avoid the problem of false regression, which can occur when the residuals series are highly correlated. This means that the findings can show a statistically significant association between variables when there is none, which can be deceptive (Verbeek, 2012). To establish a valid VECM model with all of these variables, they must be integrated in the same order, i.e. differentiated equally many times to become stationary. In addition, we investigated the long run equilibrium by testing our VAR models for cointegration. If there is evidence of cointegration, a VECM can be computed. Finally, we ran the variance decomposition to see how the shocks of the variables influence each other.

Augmented Dickey-Fuller test

Stationarity is important since it requires that the distribution of the variables employed not change over time, which means that the mean, variance, and covariance should be consistent across time. We started by using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test (ADF) to determine the presence of unit roots in our time series data. This was accomplished using the Pantula Principle, which states that the highest suspected order of integration should be checked first until the null hypothesis cannot be rejected (Pantula, 1989). As a result, we first tested for integration of order three against integration of order two, then

integration of order two against integration of order one, and finally integration of order one against integration of order zero until the null hypothesis could not be rejected. We tried it for all lag durations between zero and five.

The ADF test can be performed with or without a trend (Dickey and Fuller, 1981). We selected to include a constant and a trend, followed by merely a constant, in order to be certain of the outcome, as this is typically done in the field. As a result, the ADF-test process took the following shape, with constant and trend parameters.

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \rho y_{t-1} + \beta \bar{t} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where Δy_t in the model is the first difference, α refers to the existence of a drift term, k is the number of lags, β is the coefficient of the linear time trend \bar{t} , and with only constant,

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \rho y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \gamma_i \Delta y_{t-i} + \epsilon_t \quad (4)$$

Where Δy_t in the model is the first difference, α is the constant, which is distinct from zero $\alpha \neq 0$ and ϵ_t is the residual. If the series is an integrated process, the null hypothesis refers to $\rho = 0$, and ϵ_t is the series' residual. It is checked to see if it is zero. If $\rho = 0$, the series is an integrated process, and if $\rho \neq 0$, the reverse is considered. The null hypothesis of the ADF unit root test is that there is no stationarity (i.e., $\rho = 0$) in the variables, while the alternative is that there is stationarity (i.e., $\rho \neq 0$). As a result, if the null hypothesis is rejected, we can conclude that there is no unit root in our series. Different information criteria are proposed to determine the best number of lag lengths. We picked Akaike's information criteria since it is widely accepted (Verbeek, 2012).

Sims (1980) developed the VAR model to improve accuracy in multivariate data. The VAR model is defined as a statistical description of an economic system. In our scenario, the economic system consists of five variables, with the VAR describing the data series of the variables and their interactions with their own historical observations.

In addition, our model is referred to as linear since VAR generates linear interdependencies across time series without the necessity for a difference between endogenous and exogenous variables (Verbeek, 2012). As a result, all variables in our model are regarded as endogenous. As previously explained, all variables must have the same lag structure in order to be included in a VAR system. As a result, a model based on an underlying structure can be described in a so-called reduced form.

$$x_t = \sum_{i=1}^k \Pi_i x_{t-i} + \Psi D_t + e_t \quad (5)$$

where Π_i is the matrix of coefficients for lag number i , k is the lag length that all variables have, x_t is the vector of the variables, the vector of the variables is represented as x_{ti} , D_t is a vector of deterministic variables that includes constant terms, seasonal dummies, and other dummies, and e_t is the vector system's residual. We tried for zero to a maximum of eight lags to discover the ideal lag length for the VAR model and chose the ultimate lag number based on AIC. Too many lags diminish the degrees of freedom, which reduces the model's explanatory power and may create multicollinearity, whereas too few lags raise specification mistakes and erroneous results (Sjö, 2019).

Johansen test cointegration

The Johansen test cointegration, proposed by Johansen (1988), aims to investigate the co-movement of a stationary process among variables and whether or not they have a linear connection, i.e. are moving in the same direction. If cointegration is discovered, it means that the variables have a long-run relationship and have common trends, forming a linear steady state (Sjö, 2019). In fact, this means that even if shock events disrupt movement in the individual series in the near run, they will still converge with time. The

first step was to look at the rank of the α -matrix, which refers to cointegrated vectors in the long run (Verbeek, 2012). This is decided by the major eigenvalues. We used the Trace statistics to determine the significance of the α -matrix, which is defined as

$$\lambda_{trace}(r) = -T \sum_{i=r+1}^k \log(1 - \lambda_i) \quad (6)$$

where r represents the number of cointegrated vectors or linear steady state relations among the variables, k is the number of variables in the system, and the null hypotheses are defined as follows.

$$H_0: r = 0$$

$$H_1: r < k$$

where H_0 indicates of no cointegration and H_1 indicates of cointegration. Hence, the reduced rank is defined as $0 < r < k$, and if the rank equals zero, that would have implied no cointegration and non-stationary variables. If at least two of the variables in the system are cointegrated, we can proceed to a VECM.

Engel and Granger (1987) presented and developed the model, which provides a differentiated variation of the VAR model. When estimating the VECM, we lowered the number of delays in our VAR models by one. Aside from the short run dynamics, which are of importance for this investigation, the VECM also describes the long run relationship between the variables. The VECM is written in the following format:

$$\Delta x_t = \Pi x_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k-1} \Gamma_i \Delta x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (7)$$

where x_t , x_{t-1} is the matrix of cointegrated vectors, called the error-correction term (ECM) and captures the long run dynamics of the equation, the short run dynamics are represented in the second term where ε_t is the vector of the variables, $k-1$ indicates that we lose one lag when converting from a VAR to a VECM. The residual diagnostic tests that were done on all VAR models were likewise performed on all vector error-correction models.

Granger's (1969) non-causality test was used. If a cointegration relationship is discovered among the variables, then implies that Granger causality must exist in at least one direction (Sjö, 2019). The test is described as follows: if one variable x_t causes another variable y_t , then the lagged values of x_t must predict y_t . Specifically, the results can inform us if the stock market drives the housing market, or vice versa, or possibly both. This is known as a non-causality test because Granger (1969), who invented it, argued that we can only test if one variable is not causing another because the future cannot foresee the present or the past.

The Granger causality test can be illustrated in the following form (Sjö, 2019), here as a test whether y_t Granger causes x_t

$$y_t = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i x_{t-i} + e_{1t} \quad (8)$$

where the lagged values of y_t and x_t explains the y_t , and a test whether x_t Granger causes y_t

$$x_t = \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha_i y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i x_{t-i} + e_{2t} \quad (9)$$

If the parameter is different from zero, $\beta \neq 0$, in each case, we can understand that x_t predicts or Granger causes y_t and vice versa. This is accomplished by an F-test, which examines the joint significance of the β parameters (Sjö, 2019). However, even if one of these tests is dubbed the Granger cause, its significance does not entail causes because we cannot rule out the opposite.

Results and Analysis

The link between the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines was analyzed using cointegration and error correction modeling methodologies. Cointegration analysis was used to test for the long-term equilibrium relationship between the PSEi and RREPI, while error correction modeling was used to examine the short-term dynamics between the two markets.

The study results show that the Philippine real estate and stock markets are highly integrated, suggesting that they are not effective diversification tools for investors. The results indicate that while both markets are good alternatives for investment allocation, investors cannot gain the benefits of diversity by building a portfolio that includes both the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines.

The descriptive statistics and unit root tests are examined first in the empirical analysis. The Johansen cointegration is then used to assess the long-run relationship, and the VECM is used to evaluate the cointegrated series' long-run and short-run qualities. Tables I and II contain descriptive statistics that indicate the association between the series. The mean of the LPSE reveals that the quarterly change in stock prices is 8.2 percent higher

Date: 04/18/23 Time: 00:26 Sample: 2000Q1 2022Q1			
	LHPI	LIR	LPSE
Mean	4.730098	-0.009403	8.200395
Median	4.629058	0.073843	8.318759
Maximum	5.591465	0.473417	9.054671
Minimum	3.824740	-1.003362	6.925998
Std. Dev.	0.432279	0.440361	0.684379
Skewness	-0.027516	-0.741569	-0.376587
Kurtosis	2.013847	2.639863	1.657291
Jarque-Bera	3.617576	8.638181	8.789266
Probability	0.163853	0.013312	0.012343
Sum	420.9787	-0.836850	729.8351
Sum Sq. Dev.	16.44410	17.06476	41.21698
Observations	89	89	89

when compared to real estate and interest rate, although the real estate market gives an average quarterly change of 4.7 percent during the same period. Furthermore, stock price volatility is larger than that of real estate.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Unit root test

Table 3 shows the results of the ADF (Dickey and Fuller, 1981) and PP (Phillips and Perron, 1988) unit root tests. Both tests failed to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root at the 1% significance level for all variables that demonstrate stationarity and indicate an integration of order one, or I(1).

According to Engle and Granger (1987), a linear combination of series with an order of integration of one may be stationary, in which case the cointegration test can be applied to the variables to investigate any possible long-run equilibrium relationships.

	Augmented Dickey-Fuller		Phillips-Perron	
Variable	Level	1 st Difference	Level	1 st Difference
PSEi	0.8086	0.0000	0.8065	0.0001
RRepi	0.3477	0.0000	0.3227	0.0000
LIR	0.1147	0.0000	0.0018	0.0000

Table 3 Unit root test results

Cointegration test results

The results of the cointegration analysis indicated that there was a long-term equilibrium relationship between the PSEI and RREPI. The Johansen cointegration test revealed a significant rank of one, indicating the presence of a single cointegrating vector at the 5% level of significance.

The Johansen cointegration test (Johansen and Juselius, 1990, Johansen, 1991) was used to examine the cointegration between PSEI and RREPI, NCR and ONCR. The test has an intercept and a linear trend but no exogenous variables. Based on the LR, FPE, AIC, and HQ criteria, the ideal lag length is determined to be seven. The trace test reveals cointegrating equations at the 0.01 level, indicating the presence of cointegration among the variables. According to the results of the cointegration test, the stock market and real estate market are integrated, with no segmentation between the two markets. This finding has significant implications for portfolio management. Due to the integration of the two markets, they will exhibit comparable return patterns in the long run, meaning that there is no risk reduction benefit to holding both stocks and real estate in the same portfolio.

Johansen Cointegration Test

Testing hypothesis	Eigenvalue	Trace statistics	5% Critical Value	Prob.
$H_0=0$ and $r=1$ (None)	0.40	56.22	29.79	0.0000*

H₀=0 and r=1(At most 1)	0.02	2.36	15.49	0.19
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Note: * and ** denote rejection of the null hypothesis at the 0.01 and 0.05 level respectively.

Trace test indicates 1 cointegrating eqn (s) at the 0.05 level

In the VECM estimate, it reveals a long-run link between the stock and real estate markets. The rate of adjustment is statistically significant at 1% (t statistics = -3.2) and has a negative sign (-0.08). This implies that the short-run values of stock prices converge to their long-run equilibrium level at an 8% rate due to the contribution of the real estate market. The result supported the findings of Yousaf and Ali (2020), Lou (2017) and Gokmenoglu and Hesami (2019).

The coefficient of the error correction term is significant at the 1% level or higher with a negative sign, confirming the cointegration test conclusion of a long run relationship. This means that variations in house prices are a result of disequilibrium in the cointegrating connection. The coefficient on the error correction term denotes the rate at which housing prices adjust to the long-run equilibrium. The adjustment speed is -0.08 in Model 1 and -0.07 in Model 2. A value of 8% implies that a deviation from the long run equilibrium level of property prices in one quarter is rectified by around 8% in the next quarter. A value of 7% indicates that house values adjust at a rate of 7% every quarter to restore equilibrium when there is a disturbance to the steady-state relationship. This finding is similar to those of Lean and Smyth (2013) and Ibrahim (2010), who investigated the association between property prices and stock prices in Malaysia and Thailand, respectively.

According to Young and Hostee (2017), using control variables in a model enhances robustness testing and is likely to reduce biased results. Adding LIR as a control variable verifies the original model's result. The long run coefficient is negative and statistically significant (t statistics=-3.2), and the sign is negative (-0.07). The coefficient for LHPI in this model is -0.57, which is close to the finding in the previous model (-0.54), whereas the coefficient for LIR is positive and significant. These findings are consistent with those of Finter et al. (2012), who discovered a considerable positive link between the interest rate and the stock market.

In summary, for all models, the predicted sign of the error correction term is between 0 and -1, and it is highly significant. When the control variable is included, the ECT remain, which confirms the findings from the cointegration test that there is a long run relationship.

Error Correction Modeling:

VECM Estimates		
Dependent →	LHPI	LPSE
LHPI	1.0000	-1.74 (0.13)
LPSE	-0.57** (0.04)	1.0000
LIR	-0.47* (0.07)	0.83 (0.13)
c	-0.04	0.07

Notes: All variables are expressed in natural logged and two decimal places. LHPI = house prices in the Philippines. LPSE= stock index, LIR= interest rate. *, ** and *** indicates significance at 10%-level, 5%-level, and 1% level, respectively

Long Run Determinants of House Price

LHPI $HP\% = 0.041 - 0.57LPSE - 0.47$

Long Run Determinants of Stock Price

LPSE $HP\% = -.072 + 1.74 - 0.83$

Notes: All variables are expressed in natural logged and two decimal places. LHPI = house prices in the Philippines. LPSE= stock index, LIR= interest rate. *, ** and *** indicates significance at 10%-level, 5%-level, and 1% level, respectively

Table __ Results of VECM

Dependent →	VECM Estimates	
	LHPI	LPSE
ECT _{t-1}		
LHPI	-0.07 [-6.5]*	-0.39 (-1.79)
LPSE	-0.14** (0.04)	
LIR	-0.016 (-1.16)	0.057** (1.52)

Notes: All variables are expressed in natural logged and two decimal places. LHPI = house prices in the Philippines. LPSE= stock index, LIR= interest rate. *, ** and *** indicates significance at 10%-level, 5%-level, and 1% level, respectively

Table _ Short Run Estimates

Causality tests

To analyze the dynamic behavior of stock and real estate prices further, we examine the nature of the Granger causality between real estate prices and stock prices using the estimation results of the threshold error correction model. Table 7 shows the results of the causality tests. The study focuses on the two dependent variables, LHPI index and stock index. We derive conclusions based on two t-statistics that separately test for the absence of causality. When real estate prices are the dependent variable, the significance of the t-tests indicates the existence of Granger causation from stock prices to real estate prices. When stock price is the dependent variable, however, the F statistics associated with the aforesaid threshold regime are small, showing that Granger causation from real estate prices to stock prices does not exist. Overall, these findings indicate that a wealth effect, but not a credit-price effect, existed during the period. This suggests that home prices are rather high, and real estate is used considerably more as an investment vehicle.

Granger Causality Test		
Dependent	LHPI	LPSE
ECT _{t-1}		
LHPI	-	3.2* (0.07)
LPSE	11.06*** (0.0009)	
LIR	0.014 (70.54)	0.000 (0.99)

Notes: All variables are expressed in natural logged and two decimal places. LHPI = house prices in the Philippines. LPSE= stock index, LIR= interest rate. *, ** and *** indicates significance at 10%-level, 5%-level, and 1% level, respectively

Table _ Granger causality test under VECM

Conclusion

In conclusion, the results of this study suggest a strong relationship between the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines. The analysis showed that stock prices tend to outperform housing prices, indicating the presence of a wealth effect. This finding suggests that the stock market is crucial to the stability of the real estate industry.

Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of considering both real estate and stock investments in a diversified portfolio. Although both asset classes provide diversification benefits, investors cannot achieve optimal diversification by building a portfolio that includes both the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines.

Also, findings indicate that a wealth effect, but not a credit-price effect, existed during the period. This suggests that home prices are rather high, and real estate is used considerably more as an investment vehicle.

Finally, it is important to note that this study is not without limitations. The analysis was limited to a specific period, and the results may not be applicable to other time periods. Additionally, other factors such as inflation, and government policies may affect the relationship between the two markets, and future research should consider these variables. Nevertheless, this study provides important insights into the relationship between the real estate and stock markets in the Philippines and can inform investment decisions.

Recommendations:

Further research can be conducted to explore the impact of other factors, such as inflation rates and government policies, on the relationship between the stock and real estate markets in the Philippines. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the factors that influence the performance of these markets and how they interact with each other.

Also, investors should carefully consider the relationship between the stock and real estate markets when making investment decisions. Diversification across asset classes may not provide the expected benefits if the markets are highly integrated, as is the case with the Philippine stock-real estate markets nexus. It is important to assess the risk-return characteristics of each market and determine the optimal allocation for a given investment portfolio.

Further, policymakers should monitor the performance of the stock and real estate markets and take measures to promote stability and growth. The close relationship between these markets highlights the importance of a coordinated approach to policy-making that takes into account the interdependence of different sectors of the economy. The Philippine government could explore measures to increase access to real estate investment opportunities for a broader range of investors, such as the strengthening of REITs or other real estate investment vehicles. This would not only provide investors with greater diversification opportunities but also contribute to the development of the real estate market and the broader economy.

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